

Ultrasonic Studies of some Substituted Diketones in Binary Solutions of Water with Dioxane and Tetrahydrofuran

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Manuscript received 22 April 1993, revised 5 October 1993, accepted 12 October 1993

The apparent molal compressibilities (ϕ_K) and the apparent molal volumes (ϕ_V) of the diketones (1-3) have been evaluated by the measurement of ultrasonic sound velocities and densities in 50, 60, 70, and 80% dioxane-water and THF-water mixtures. The results are discussed in the light of solute-solvent interactions. ϕ_K and ϕ_V values suggest that ion-solvent interactions become less on addition of water. The limiting apparent molal volumes (ϕ_V^0) have been determined in dilute solutions (0.005-0.008 M).

β -Diketones are well known for their biological activity. A few propan-1,3-diones are known to occur in plants. They are precursors in the biosynthesis of flavonoids. Understanding the behaviour of such organics in dilute solutions is most helpful in tracing the path of physiological processes. Ultrasonic parameters are being extensively used to study molal interactions in pure liquids¹, liquid mixtures² and electrolytic solutions³. The study of apparent molal volumes (ϕ_V) and apparent molal compressibilities (ϕ_K) can furnish useful information on the nature of solute-solvent interactions⁴. Behaviour of carbohydrates and sodium salts of higher fatty acids in dilute aqueous solutions is studied by Kaulgud *et al.*^{5,6}. A number of workers^{7,8} used isentropic compressibility to know the interactions in binary mixtures. Rambabu *et al.*⁹ studied volumetric and ultrasonic behaviour of an alcohol with γ -butyrolactone.

In case of diketones (1-3), systematic variation of these parameters with slow addition of water to their solutions is yet to be explored. In order to know about the solute-solvent interactions, the apparent molal compressibilities (ϕ_K) and apparent molal volumes (ϕ_V) of 1-(2-hydroxyphenyl)-3-

phenyl-1,3-propanedione (1), 1-(2-hydroxy-5-methylphenyl)-3-phenyl-1,3-propanedione (2) and 1-(2-hydroxy-5-methylphenyl)-3-(4'-methoxy)phenyl-1,3-propanedione (3) were determined by measuring their sound velocities and densities in 50, 60, 70 and 80% of dioxane-water (D-W), and tetrahydrofuran-water (THF-W) mixtures. The limiting apparent molal volumes (ϕ_V^0) of these diketones have also been evaluated in 50% solvent-water mixtures at low concentration region (0.005-0.008 M). The values of ϕ_V^0 have been used to discuss the interactions of ions in the medium of different dielectric constants.

Results and Discussion

The values of ϕ_K and ϕ_V are listed in Tables 1 and 2 respectively. The values of limiting parameter ϕ_V^0 are presented in Table 3. The ϕ_V vs \sqrt{m} plots show the linear variation at 30°. Similarly it has been observed that ϕ_K varies linearly with mole fraction of dioxane and THF. The salient aspects of the results are (i) decrease in compressibility ϕ_K , on addition of water in all the solvent-water mixtures, (ii) increase in ϕ_V values on addition of water and (iii) rise

in ϕ_V^0 values on introducing the bulkier groups like methyl and methoxy in diketones.

TABLE 1—APPARENT MOLAL COMPRESSIBILITIES (ϕ_K) OF SUBSTITUTED DIKETONES IN DIFFERENT COMPOSITIONS OF ORGANIC SOLVENT AND WATER

Diketone	Medium	$\phi_K \times 10^4 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ bar}^{-1}$			
		50%	60%	70%	80%
1	D-W	-156.42	-145.81	-115.14	-87.52
	THF-W	-122.23	-123.13	-112.08	-100.35
2	D-W	-160.88	-142.17	-126.06	-95.56
	THF-W	-122.81	-111.66	-101.57	-65.75
3	D-W	-154.07	-134.10	-112.11	-92.93
	THF-W	-144.98	-125.08	-110.50	-98.73

TABLE 2—APPARENT MOLAL VOLUMES (ϕ_V) OF SUBSTITUTED DIKETONES IN DIFFERENT COMPOSITIONS OF ORGANIC SOLVENT AND WATER

Diketone	Medium	$\phi_V \text{ cm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$			
		50%	60%	70%	80%
1	D-W	119.76	-227.84	-582.27	-915.65
	THF-W	1096.84	731.58	332.02	-64.23
2	D-W	131.44	-212.19	-563.85	-905.82
	THF-W	1110.40	745.09	345.48	-50.84
3	D-W	160.56	-182.48	-535.19	-873.34
	THF-W	1139.45	774.036	374.30	-22.13

TABLE 3—LIMITING APPARENT MOLAL VOLUMES (ϕ_V^0) OF SUBSTITUTED DIKETONES IN 50% ORGANIC SOLVENT-WATER MIXTURE

Diketone	Medium	$\phi_V^0 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$
1	D-W	410
	THF-W	1358
2	D-W	445
	THF-W	1420
3	D-W	495
	THF-W	1530

Jahagirdar and Pankanti¹⁰ reported that ϕ_K of amino acids in acetone-water and dioxane-water media decreases upto 40% of solvent-water mixture. However, they observed the rise in ϕ_K values in 40% mixture and above. The same trend was observed for calcium acetate in different percentage of acetic acid-water mixture by Blokhra and Lomash¹¹. Present study reveals increase in ϕ_K values above 50% solvent-water mixtures. It is observed that ϕ_K becomes more and more negative on addition of water in all the solvent-water

mixtures. This suggests that the organic solvent becomes less compressible with ions in the lower percentage of solvent-water mixtures. Hence it is clear that the interactions between solute and solvent become less on addition of water due to breaking of the sheath of the solvent surrounding the ions. As a result, the association between solute and solvent is decreased. It is also evident from the high solubility of these diketones in pure solvent and precipitation of solute on further dilution of 50% mixture with water. This fact is also supported by the study of their apparent molal volumes. It is observed that the ϕ_V values fall with the increase in percentage of organic solvent, i.e. ϕ_V values are found to increase on addition of water. This gives direct idea about the decrease in solvation of solute by solvent on dilution with water and hence minimum solute-solvent interactions.

The limiting parameter ϕ_V^0 is obtained in 50% of the dioxane-water and THF-water mixtures, in the dilute solutions (0.005–0.008 M). ϕ_V^0 values are found to increase in the following order of solvents : THF-W > D-W. This suggests the maximum solvation in THF-water mixture than dioxane-water mixture. Hence the solute-solvent interactions are maximum in THF-water mixture which is the medium of low dielectric constant. It is interesting to note that ϕ_V^0 increases with the decrease in dielectric constant and hence ion-solvent interactions would also be more and consequently ϕ_V^0 will be larger¹².

It has also been observed that ϕ_V^0 values increase from diketone (1) to diketone (3) in all the organic solvent-water mixtures. This may be ascribed to the presence of methyl group in diketone 2 and both methyl and methoxy groups in diketone 3 due to which interstitial accommodation of these groups in solvent groups is not favourable. Hence there is negative contribution towards ϕ_V^0 values on introducing these bulky groups, as also reported for other systems by some workers¹³.

Experimental

The diketones (1–3) were prepared by standard method¹⁴ and crystallised from ethanol. Purity of the compounds was checked by conductometric titration, m.p., tlc, ir and pmr spectra. All the solutions were prepared by weight in mixing bottles. The solvents dioxane and THF were purified by standard procedure¹⁵ and different compositions were prepared using double-distilled water.

For the accurate measurement of densities, three sets of pycnometers having different volumes were used. Pycnometers were standardised with all-glass distilled water at 25°. The density was measured with an accuracy of 0.00001. The densities of solvents are in well agreement with literature value¹⁶.

Ultrasonic velocity measurements : The sound velocities were measured differentially using an ultrasonic interferometer (M-81, Mittal Enterprises) with the measuring frequency of 4 MHz and the frequency tolerance $\pm 0.3\%$. The accuracy of the instrument was examined with double-distilled water. The observed value of sound velocity 1500.48 m s⁻¹ at 25° was in satisfactory agreement with the literature value (1496.63 m s⁻¹). All the measurements were made at constant temperature employing a thermostatic bath ($\pm 0.01\%$).

From the values of sound velocities and densities the apparent molal compressibilities (ϕ_K) were calculated by the expression,

$$\phi_K = \frac{1000(\beta_s d_o - \beta_o d_s)}{m d_s d_o} + \frac{\beta_s M}{d_s}$$

Apparent molal volumes (ϕ_V) were calculated by finding difference in densities of solvent and solution, molecular weight and molarity using the relation,

$$\phi_V = \frac{M}{d} + \frac{(d_o - d) 10^3}{m d d_o}$$

The limiting apparent molal volumes ϕ_V^o in 50% solvent-water mixture at different concentrations of diketones (0.005–0.008 M) were obtained by extrapolating ϕ_V vs \sqrt{m} curves to zero concentration, as the solutions are very dilute.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Principal, Government Vidarbha Mahavidyalaya, and to Principal, College of Engineering, Badnera, for facilities.

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